

THE IMPORTANCE OF CREATIVE WORKS DURING THE TIME OF AMIR TEMUR (IN THE CASE OF THE SHAHRISABZ STATE MUSEUM RESERVE)

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Annotation: In this article, the author notes that Amir Timur's enormous contribution to the state system, the development of science, education and culture. During the reign of the Temurids, there was a flourishing not only of art crafts, but also of books, calligraphy, art of miniature, several schools of miniaturists existed at once. There is evidence that there was a rich library, a collection of books from all the conquered countries.

Keywords: great figures, of the Temurid period, ribbed dome, architectural structures, archeological structures, museum expositions, miniature art, jewelry, astronomical instruments, rich library.

Shahrisabz from antiquity to the present day. The ancient and sacred land of Shahrisabz is a holy place. On this earth lived the ancestors of such great figures as Khisrav Dekhlavi, Mirza Bedil, Mirza Golib. But this region was most of all glorified by the great commander Amir Temur. "During the reign of Amir Temur and the Temurid dynasty, the art of diplomacy was raised to a high level. This is confirmed by diplomatic relations and correspondence of Sahibkiran with the rulers of France, England, Spain, Byzantium, Egypt, China, India, the Ottoman Empire and many other states. It is well known from history that dozens of ambassadors from around the world, including European ones, arrived at the [7:1492-1495] palace of Amir Temur.

The sources of that time noted that in the period 1389-1398, that is, for almost 10 years, ambassadors were sent to China on behalf of Amir Temur 9 times. The annals contain the names of ambassadors [8:135-138] representing Amir Temur and the state of Temurids in Europe and Asia - Muhammad Keshi hailing from Shakhrisabz, as well as Mavlono Hafiz, Giesiddin Nakkosh, Abdurazzak Samarkandi. Unfortunately, their life and work are not fully understood and are waiting for their researchers," said President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev [1].

During his reign, such unique [9:1-6] architectural structures were built as the Ak-Saray Palace, the Gur Emir Mausoleum, the Bibi-Khanym Mosque, the Khoja Ahmad

Yasavi Mausoleum and another mausoleum in Shahe Zinda. The most grandiose palace is Aksaray, built 24 years, according to the plan of Timur, Shakhrisabz was to become the[10:96-100] capital of the whole world. At the moment, only the input has been preserved the portal of this palace, its height is 36 meters, in the original it was 70 meters in height.

During the reign of the Temurids, there was a flourishing of not only artistic craft, but also book business, calligraphy, and[11:128-131] miniature art; several miniature schools existed at once. There is evidence that there was a rich library, a collection of books from all the conquered countries.

In Shakhrisabz, in connection with the 660th anniversary of Amir Temur, construction work began on the breakdown of the Amir Temur square in the city center, while archaeological research was[12:128-132] conducted at the Ak-Saray and Dorussiadat complexes[2].

Amir Temur, according to the order of the Department of Cultural Affairs of Kashkadarya region. In September 1997, with the support of the joint European project "Tarih" ("History"), Exeter University (England), Ren II University (France), Frederksberg Seminary (Denmark) and Mirzo Ulugbek NUUZ in Shakhrisabz, a scientific and theoretical conference was held at topic "Central Asia and Europe in the era of Amir Temur and[13:73-76] Temurids". Scientists from 14 countries of Europe and Central Asia took part in it. Particular attention was paid to archaeological materials testifying to the location and formation of the early city in the Kitabo-Shakhrisabz oasis in the 8th-7th centuries[3].

The Museum of the History of Material Culture named after Amir Temur in ancient times, Shakhrisabz was called by historians[14] and geographers as Nautaka, and in the Middle Ages the city of Kesh. In written sources there are such names as "Dilkash", "Kubbatul ilm val adab". During the years of independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan (1996) in honor of the 660th anniversary of the great commander Amir Temur, on the initiative representatives of the local intelligentsia, a museum of the history of material culture was created, in the fund of which more than 21,000 works of art are stored. The main goal of the museum is to study the history of the development of the city's culture.

The museum provides mock-ups of these architectural structures, which testify to the power of the state of the Temurids. The main idea of the museum is to convey the greatness of Amir Temur and the spirit of the[15:86-90] Temurids.

The museum building is a synthesis of the Timurid period and modern architectural style. The buildings of the Museum were created in the image of the palaces of that time and are a monument. The building has a round shape with a large ribbed dome, covered with aivan with columns in a circle. Amir Temur is the founder of a powerful centralized empire, which included 27 states.

The museum is decorated with copies of [16:292-296] samples of Zafar-Name miniatures, manuscripts "Laying of Temur", "Hams" by Alisher Navoi and "Nafta Avrang" by Abdurakhman Jami. You can also see minted coins from Bukhara, Samarkand, Teremez and Herat, which depict the coat of arms of Amir Temur. The exposition of the museum includes shirk items from ceramics and copper, bronze, armaments, jewelry and astronomical instruments of Ulugbek, gold sewing robes and many other items from the time of the Timurids dynasty.

The museum building is located in the complex of Chubin Madrasah, built in the XIV-XVI centuries and included [17:686-692] in the UNESCO list of "Universal values". In written sources of the era of Amir Temur and Timurids, it is noted that in the city, at that time, there were more than 40 madrasahs and mosques in which both religious and world sciences were taught. In this regard, the architectural structures of the madrasah are interesting to use as a museum [4].

The exposition of the museum is located in a closed two-story building, built in the 19th century and part of the [18:342-346] Chubin madrasah complex and on the terrace of the madrasah. The exposition on the ground floor is called "Shahrisabz - the same age as the Avesta". This exhibition covers the period of the appearance of the first city, the first intelligent person (Homo sapiens sapiens) in Central Asia and the period of development until the XIV century. There are exhibits such as world famous assuaries with the image of the prophet Zarathushtra, figurines depicting Anahita, figurines of idols, a set of pottery of the ancient period. On the 2nd floor, the city moved to a new place (starting from the 9th-11th centuries), the dynasty of Amir Temur and Timurids, the art of decorating [19:223-236] architectural monuments erected during the Timurids, mosaics and majolica, the art of Islam and the books of the Koran, clay decorated dishes of the period Timurids and ethnography of Shakhrisabz, as well as the overall layout of the city, erected in the era of the Timurids [5]. Aivan presents samples of grave stones of the Timurids era, processed as a work of high art, the work of stonecutters. Wood carving (14th century carved door made for the tomb of Shamsiddin Kulol) and large clay jugs.

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